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Exploring Need-Patterns amongst Generations : A Review-Based Paper

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Abstract

Need is an outcome of biological and psychological drive. While understanding the concept of needs within individuals, it is also necessary to evaluate the gaps between generations as well, as they share common experiences involving social and historical processes, which probably can depict the outcome of period-effect and a common ground of development. As compared to the cohorts of previous generations, the need patterns of the most recent generation always appear to us to be typical. However, we frequently become aware of the fact that we have strayed into what previous generations would have considered abnormal, and from that place of enigma, we generate a solution to return to the situation or in that specific time context where any specific need-pattern will be categorised as being normal or socially appropriate. This may result in the dynamism of need patterns that vary from generation to generation. This paper focuses on whether there has been a fundamental change in the need-patterns or any other change that can be seen across generations and emphasises the need to develop a sophisticated social psychology paradigm to overcome the issue of generational differentiation and to distinguish between the generations that constitute society.

Keywords Generations, Needs, Need-Pattern.

Introduction

The concept of Generation

The seminal work "The Problem of Generations" by Karl Mannheim, published in the early 20th century, constituted one of the pioneering efforts to delineate the concept of a generation. A generation, in this context, refers to a group of individuals who share similar age brackets and have experienced the same historical context and events. Therefore, the environment that they encounter during their formative years influences their values, attitudes, and behavioural patterns (Ng & Johnson, 2015).

Freud and Jung, despite their disagreements, believed that any psychology-related discipline must include a mechanism to account for the transmission of personality traits or individual patterns of thought and behaviour between generations. Due to his predisposition in favour of scientific materialism, Freud proposed that "ego-structures" were passed down and kept as a result of our intricate phylogeny (Loizzo, 2011).

Objective of study

The paper aims to explore generational differences in need patterns and their impact on attitudes and motivations. It highlights the need for a refined social psychology paradigm to address generational differentiation.

Review of Literature

Many books and literature have been reviewed for this paper which are discussed through out the paper.

Main Text Modern Approaches to Generational Classification

The notion of age often leads to misinterpretations when discussing different generations. Instead of considering current age, the classification of generational cohorts is based on the year of birth. A refined social psychology paradigm can overcome the challenge of generational differentiation by viewing a generation as a relatively autonomous social group of individuals united by a shared cultural-historical context and common experiences. According to Sivrikova (2015), the following factors should be taken into account to differentiate between the generations that constitute society: historical era, age, family role, and generational identity.

Robbins and Judge (2013), in their book *Organizational Behavior*, classified generations into the following categories:

1. Generation X (Born between 1965–1980)
2. Generation Y/Millennials (Born between 1981- 1996)
3. Generation Z (Born between 1997-2012)

Factors Influencing Generational Differences

The generation Xers were born following World War II, when warriors were welcomed and the economy boomed. From the 1960s through the middle of the 1980s, Xers started working. They carried a significant amount of the "hippie ethic" and a mistrust of authority with them. Yet they prioritise success in terms of money and accomplishment.

Pragmatists put in a lot of effort and desire to reap the rewards of their labour because they feel that objectives may justify methods. They only view the companies they work in as platforms for their careers. They place high importance on terminal values, such as a sense of success and social acceptance (Robbins & Judge, 2013).

Globalisation, working parents, MTV, AIDS, and computers have all had a significant impact on the lives of millenials (Generation Yers). The pursuit of professional happiness, versatility, and life alternatives is important to Generation Y. Relationships as well as the family are crucial. You are sceptics and millenials when it comes to authority. They also liked working in teams. Yers are less inclined to make personal sacrifices when it comes to their company than earlier generations due to a need for balance in their lives. They score well on the RVS for genuine friendship, joy, and enjoyment (Robbins & Judge, 2013).

The Z-Generation, which had just begun to enter the workforce, was born during a period of economic prosperity. They are also known as Netters, Nexters, Generation-Z, and Generation Nexters. They have quality standards and look for purposes in their jobs. Compared to Generation Xers and millenials, they are more focused on achieving wealth and fame (81 percent and 51 percent, respectively); however, they regard themselves as socially conscious. They are the first cohort to consider technology casual and are comfortable with diversification. They are more likely than earlier generations to be inquisitive, electronically connected, and enterprising and are also characterised as entitled and dependent by some. They could disagree with other generations on communication and business dress. They enjoy criticism as well (Robbins & Judge, 2013).

In today's world, social and cultural events have significantly changed and are constantly changing within generational cohorts. The investigation of distinct impacts among various generations should be regarded as important. Life cycle effects (also known as age effects), period effects, and cohort effects are three different influences that can cause variations in attitudes and motivations between age groups (Glenn, 1977; Brady & Elms, 1999). "When the life cycle effect is at work, disparities between younger and older individuals are primarily related to their different positions in the life cycle, whereas differences between younger and older people are mostly due to their respective positions in the life cycle." Period effects are seen when events and conditions (for example, wars, social movements, economic booms or busts, scientific or technical discoveries), as well as larger societal factors (for example, the increasing visibility of homosexuality) coincide.

Life events have an impact on people, according to Lancaster and Stillman (2002), and this influences behaviour. These occurrences will influence the individual's assumptions and views. According to Jeffris and Hunte (2004), a cohort group's response to historical events that modify the social environment is determined by their stage of life at the time of the occurrences. Besides that, a cohort's collective response is shaped by how and

when they were raised, resulting in significant variation in interpretation of the event and the resulting response/behaviour from one generational cohort group to the next. Social movements, economic booms or busts, scientific or technological breakthroughs), as well as broader social forces (such as the growing visibility of gays and lesbians in society), impact everyone, regardless of age. Period impacts are considered to have long-breakthrough for a whole population." (The Whys and Hows of Generations Research, Pew Research Centre, 2015). Generational disparities may occur as a consequence of the unique historical circumstances that people in a certain age cohort experience, notably when they are processing and developing ideas. This may be the result of a period of influence that a previous generation felt but that the following generation did not, such as the Vietnam War or various social upheavals of the 1960s and 1970s, which the newer generations did not witness since they had not yet been born. A historical event may affect individuals of a single generation in an unjustifiably significant way. This may be because it occurs during a crucial stage of life, such as adolescent years, when awareness of the outside world increases and individual identity and value systems are formed. Dinas & Stoker, 2014; Winship, 2008; Dinas & Stoker, 2014).

Furthermore, there have been theories that generations progress more circularly than linearly (Lancaster & Stillman, 2002; Howe & Strauss, 2007). Each generation divides from the one before it assesses the adult surplus of that age and substitutes the core characteristics as well as the essence of the leaving generation (Rickes, 2010). The impact of age groups (ranging from 9 to 80 years old, including children, adolescents, young adults, middle-aged adults, and old adults) on motivation and how they relate to Maslow's theory of motivation was explored. ANOVAs (Age Sex) by employing Life Motivation Scale Brown, 1981), proving showed substantial variation for Maslow's four needs on the given scale's eleven life components (Goebel & Brown, 1981), proving inter generational differences in need patterns.

Lifestyle is changing as a result of the post-industrial revolution, and much more vulnerable communities are anticipated to encounter additional needs that consist of evolving gender norms and family dynamics. being asked to provide care for an older relative who is weak or growing frail without the help of family members, as well as juggling between paid job and family obligations, primarily child care (Taylor, 2004). Industrialised cultures' age distributions are changing quickly, which is shifting conventional relationships between age groups. Some analysts believe that stereotypes of old age are now changing due to the emergence of the young-old, or people between the ages of 55 and 75, who constitute 15% of the population and are generally in good health, financially secure, largely unencumbered by traditional work and life obligations, becoming more active in politics, which is modifying perceptions of old age. This group will establish a plethora of different requirements for the purposeful utilization of time as well as for optimising chances, including both individual growth and social integration. The young and elderly have a great capacity to alter societal change by fostering a trial culture and therefore fostering better relationships across generations (Neugarten,1974).The perplexing aspects of the association between youth and society are explored in this study by Wyn and White (2000), which makes the case that researchers should take into account the unique situations of the post-1970 generation when asking how social systems and economic disparity affect youth's lifestyle and should also take into account how youth react to new experiences. Furstenberg (2010) claims that compared to the years following World War II, home departure, marrying, and the beginning of parenthood all occur substantially later in life nowadays. Youngsters from all socioeconomic classes started staying in school longer, getting married later, and having children later as the well-paid industrial jobs in America vanished in the 1960s. A growing number of lower-class women selected non-marital motherhood over marriage altogether. Instead of their partners, they frequently turn to their biological families for monetary and emotional assistance. The economic and emotional stress of motherhood increased as the amount of time that young adults were dependent on their families got longer. As the shift to maturity gets increasingly drawn out, the growing family responsibility may have detrimental consequences overall. Younger people may start to see having children as increasingly difficult and much less fulfilling. People may be discouraged from having more children or any children at all if they feel the need to support them for long periods. Such choices might worsen the challenge of caring for an expanding population of the old and the young while also lowering overall fertility, eventually reducing the working population. The family structure must be strengthened, and policymakers must assist in reducing the numerous and conflicting expectations that are being imposed on parents. In a long-term study conducted by Field and Minkler (1988), social support was evaluated in a sample of 74 very old (85 years and older) or old (74 to 84 years old) participants in the Berkeley Older Generation Study. For the group as a whole, there was significant continuity in the amount of interaction between the years 1969 and 1983, especially concerning familial bonds. Men but not women, and the very old but not the very had reductions in their interactions with others outside of their immediate family. There were significant shifts in engagement or subjective degree

of commitment as well: satisfaction with children raised while involvement outside the family dropped.

Moreover, the majority of participants in research on stroke have been older than 65. This study looked at the unmet needs of stroke-affected youngsters in community housing in the UK. The majority of unmet needs are reported by people who are younger, less mobile, and therefore unable to find employment again. To enable involvement and autonomy for persons with stroke, more has to be undertaken in society, in terms of education as well as the supply of streamlined knowledge (Kersten et. al, 2018). Society search also indicated that youngsters use their parents, friends, and intimate partners to meet attachment needs (proximity-seeking, haven, and secure base). In this age group, mothers were a significant source of security. The most often used group of safe havens were best buddies. Those with weak attachments to their mothers tended to gravitate away from her and toward romantic partners. (Markiewicz, Lawford et al., 2006).

In another study, significant consistency through time was observed for several attributes, including deference and endurance, as well as broad gains for traits like achievement and autonomy, general losses for traits like affiliation and abasement, and a variety of shifts for a few selected traits. Although since the 1950s, there has been a decrease or confluence of the distinctions in personality between men and women due to generational changes that are different for each gender (Stevens & Truss, 1985). Also, social dominance (an extraverted trait), conscientiousness, and emotional stability are all traits that people exhibit an increase in, especially when they enter their early adult years (age 20 to 40). On the other hand, participants show a surge in adolescents on measures of social vitality (the second aspect of extraversion) and openness, but a decline in both of these traits in old age. Agreeableness only altered with age. Four out of the six characteristic categories showed a noticeable shift in middle and elderly age.

Extended studies and research based on younger generations exhibited a greater shift, although gender and attrition had little impact on it (Roberts & Walton, 2006).

Another study emphasises the definition of sexual diversification and the rights granted to all those who were categorised as sexual minorities (i.e., lesbian, gay, bisexual, queer, and perhaps other people who do not associate themselves with heterosexuals) and have undergone significant social transition. These advancements (such as homosexual marriages) focus on how social as well as legal changes affect sexual minorities in various ways depending on their generational era. It is evident that growing up as a member of a sexual minority in the 2010s is very different from, say, growing up as a member of a sexual minority in the 1960s, once when homosexuality remained illegal and regarded as a psychological disorder (see, for example, Hammack, Frost, Meyer, & Pletta, 2018; Russell & Fish, 2016). Hence, we can say that age has a substantial impact on attitudes toward and acceptance of sexual minorities, with younger people displaying more favourable attitudes than older ones (Frost, Meyer, & Hammack, 2015). The necessity to meet human needs probably has deep biological foundations and has cultural influences on how it is expressed. The emphasis of adolescents on autonomy and pursuit of social support are powerful expressions of the need for exploration, understanding, and taking action. These interpretations have a strong foundation in the individual's current culture. The peer influence may therefore give direction regarding what constitutes being a self-reliant adult in cultures that would provide substantial instruction and support for youngsters to undertake adult duties (Kaplan, 2002). To evaluate the prevalent motivations of higher education college students, college students in modern China were shown to have seventeen different types of motivations. They divided these reasons into three categories: self-other, or society-orientated, materialistic, biological, and spiritual, and appearance-related inner motives. Although reasons were thought to have several dimensions, the significance of the similar need might vary depending on the individual (Yangang, Xiaoyan & Liqiong, 2013). Moreover, Millennial and Generation X medical students have different needs for achievement, affiliation, and power, with Generation Xers scoring better on the motive of power, while Millennials scored higher on the motivations of achievement and affiliation. Borges, Nicole, Roldán Manuel, Carol Elam, and Bonnie Jones (2010). Younger generations, according to research, express a stronger NFU (need for uniqueness) than older generations. The disparity was evaluated instead of focusing on transient Jones (2010). ght on by a single event, it is also necessary to investigate the causal factors of China's growing propensity for the NFU and to outline the general pattern over the previous few decades (Cai, Zou, Feng, Liu and Jing, 2018). Hence, it can be stated that the necessity to meet human needs probably has deep biological foundations and has cultural influences on how it is expressed.

Implications

Human needs are the main area of attention in how evolution and culture could associate. Additionally, during the history of the human race, the methods for meeting these needs have constantly evolved and will undoubtedly continue to do so (Kaplan & Kaplan, 2002). As compared to the cohorts of previous generations, the need patterns of the most recent generation always appear to us to be typical. However, we frequently become aware of the fact that we have strayed into what previous generations would have considered abnormal, and from that place of enigma, we generate a solution to return to the situation or in that specific time context where any specific need pattern will be categorised as being normal or socially appropriate. This may result in the dynamism of need patterns that vary from generation to generation. Since each member of a generational cohort is a distinct individual. It follows that plenty of a person's peculiarities and biases may be explained by studying the characteristics and attitudes of their generational cohort (Zemke, Raines & Filipczak, 1999). Hence, we can say that it is critical to grasp the generational divide to better appreciate the concept of individual needs.

Conclusion The knowledge of need patterns within a generation and other generations must be examined to see how it influences their attitude and motivation toward any goal, as well as how they are affected by the generation to which they belong, as they share common experiences involving social and historical processes that can likely depict a common ground of development. Additionally, this type of sample can also be extrapolated to a bigger group.

In order to address the problem of generational differentiation and effectively discern between the various generations that comprise society, this paper focuses on the review of whether there has been a fundamental shift in need patterns or any other change that can be observed across generations. It also highlights the necessity of developing a sophisticated social psychology paradigm.

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